

HUNGER AND MALNUTRITION: A THREAT TO PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS' LEARNING ABILITY IN IKENNE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, OGUN STATE

Dr. PATIENCE NEMEZU CHIOMA

Department of Political Science and Public Administration, Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria. Email: chiomap@babcock.edu.ng

ENYICHUKWU GOODLUCK OGBONNA

Postgraduate Student, Department of Education, Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria. Email: ogbonnae@babcock.edu.ng

JONATHAN CHINAKA NWOSU

Professor, Department of Education, Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria. Email: nwosuj@babcock.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study looked at how malnutrition and hunger affect the learning ability of primary school pupils in Ogun State's Ikenne Local Government Area. As malnutrition and hunger continue to be a barrier to human well-being, they have a negative impact on various aspects of a child's growth and development, including their performance in the classroom hence, the purpose for the study. **Method:** In this study, a quantitative phenomenological case study design was used with focus group discussions, interview and observations as data collection instruments. One hundred and four (104) primary school learners, ten (10) teachers both male and female purposively sampled in the five school in the Local Government Area. The study is grounded in Maslow's motivational and needs theory. **Findings:** The findings showed that hunger and malnutrition had an impact on learners' physical and cognitive development, which in turn had an impact on their ability to learn, their health, and their survival. Poverty is also made worse by hunger and malnutrition since it raises the expense of medical care. The study also found that primary school students who are hungry or undernourished find it difficult to focus and learn, are less likely to attend school, and are less able to participate in physical activity and sports. **Conclusion:** Nutritional gardens should be introduced at schools, and homes. To effectively reduce hunger and malnutrition, it is essential to address their underlying causes, including socioeconomic instability, food insecurity, poverty, and population increase.

Keywords: Hunger, Malnutrition, Primary School Pupils, Learning Ability

Background of Study

The term "malnutrition" refers to a condition in which a person is lacking in any or all of the good nutritional components that are essential to good wellbeing. According to Qureshi, Bhatti and Shah, (2020), it occurs due to inadequate food supply which is needed by the body and cannot be provided because of an imbalance in those demands. According to the EFA Global Monitoring Report (UNESCO 2011), cited in Chinyoka (2014), less than half of children in sub-Saharan Africa between the age of fifteen years are underweight as a result of poor diet and malnutrition, making them more prone to illness and less able to focus in class.

Every student has the potential to do well in school. Failing to provide good nutrition puts them at risk for missing out on meeting that potential. However, taking action today to provide healthier choices in schools can help to set students up for a successful future full of possibilities. Additionally, amino acid and carbohydrate supplementation can improve perception, intuition, and reasoning. There are also a number of studies showing that improvements in nutrient intake can influence the cognitive ability and intelligence levels of school-aged children.

According to Nicola (2018) in Mind of Wonders report, what a child eat can have an impact on how the brain work as well as influences their capacity for concentration, recollection, and learning. Thus, the food an individual consumes have an influence in the mental ability and functioning of an individual. Also, according to research done by Granholm, Bimonte-Nelson, Moore, Nelson, Freeman, and Sambamurti, (2008), findings revealed that a meal rich in saturated fats impairs an individual's memory and learning abilities. This was affirmed by the Society for Neuroscience, while noting the impact of glucose and sugar as the explanation for the connection between saturated fats and mental performance. They further noted that carbohydrates contain glucose, which is crucial for giving us energy. However, foods with excessive glucose levels lower the energy level of the body.

Learning is impacted by children's nutrition as the body releases insulin when we consume glucose, which helps to break down the food we are eating (Chen, 2022). For Nicola (2018), the human body feels energized as the glucose levels increases considerably after a healthy meal. However, Nicola further posited that a high-glucose diet results in a significant decline in energy levels, which has a negative impact on how well adolescents study. This is because the body begins to shut down in order to process the entire meal due to the high level of glucose.

Hunger is an indication that a basic need is unmet, which is food. Food and/or energy is necessary for survival (Cherry, 2022) and the brain shifts into "survival mode" when an individual is hungry and concentrates on doing so rather than focusing on a task such as essay or test, which makes it more difficult to concentrate. The act of concentrating requires mental work, and much like the human muscles, the brain needs glucose to function which can be gotten from food. The human body uses hunger as a signal that you don't have enough fuel to continue moving forward. When trying to focus on mental tasks while hungry, it is similar to operating a vehicle with the gasoline gauge at zero: you may be able to get away with it for a while, but eventually you will need to stop and refuel (Edie, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

According to the National Nutrition and Health Survey, Nigeria has the second-highest prevalence of malnourished children in the world, with a nationwide prevalence rate of 32% of children under five (NNHS 2018). Only two out of every ten of the 2 million children in Nigeria who are thought to be suffering from severe acute malnutrition (SAM) are currently receiving treatment. Additionally, 7% of women of reproductive age experience acute malnutrition.

Lack of energy and focus can also result from inadequate nutrient intake. Also, some individuals experience energy slump that results from overindulging in comfort foods or treats.

On the other hand, children will naturally experience this in the same way. However, learning outcomes can be detrimental if this type of eating starts to become a regular component of a child's diet rather than just a pleasure. A better learning environment for every learner in the class may also result from improved student behavior and fewer disturbances in the classroom. Chukwu (2020) opined that although schoolchildren have poor eating habits as a result of seeing them consume foods with low nutritional quality, some kids arrive at school without eating breakfast. Some of these students are given empty food flasks and money to buy food at school, but if they are unable to do so, they frequently go without eating. Some of these children sometimes These kids resort to lying, cheating, and stealing, especially when it comes to taking food from their friends or money to buy food in order to meet their necessities of life. Since this behavior is seen as socially inappropriate by society, it causes them to become separated from loved ones and may cause them to have low self-esteem. Therefore, the feelings of the child maybe anticipated after regularly eating a snack or lunch that is high in saturated fats. The sharp decline in energy, which can also cause tiredness and irritation, can impair the child's ability to concentrate and think clearly. It's also challenging to ask children to concentrate and focus in a way that will maximize their learning while they experience this decline in energy.

Also, when there is a deficiency in a child's meal, it can have an indirect impact on his/her academic performance by increasing absences from school. Children may become more susceptible to small infections as a result of missing school (Brown et al, 2008). Based on the foregoing, this study seeks to investigate how hunger and malnutrition is a threat to primary school pupils' learning ability in Ikenne local government area of Ogun State, Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were stated to guide the study:

Ho1. Hunger and malnutrition has no significant combined threat on the child's ability to learn in school.

Ho2. There is no significant relative contribution of hunger and Malnutrition on the academic performance of primary schools pupils in Ikenne local government, area.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, a quantitative phenomenological case study design was used with focus group discussions, interview and observations as data collection instruments. One hundred and four (104) primary school learners, ten (10) teachers both male and female purposively sampled in the five school in the Local Government Area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of Hunger and Malnutrition

Under- or over-nutrition are both considered forms of malnutrition. When a person's diet falls short of what their body needs for growth and development, they are undernourished, and when they consume too many calories, they are over nourished [UNICEF, 2016]. According to World

Health Organization (2012), malnutrition addresses imbalances, excesses, or deficiencies in the amount of energy and/or nutrients a person consumes. They further noted in their report on malnutrition that the term refers to three general categories of conditions: under nutrition, which includes stunting (low height for age), wasting (low weight for height), and underweight (low weight for age); micronutrient-related malnutrition, which includes deficiencies or excesses of certain vitamins and minerals; and overweight, obesity, and non-communicable diseases associated with diet (such as heart disease, stroke, diabetes and some cancers). On the other hand, hunger is described as a state in which a person lacks the physical or financial capacity to eat enough food to satisfy fundamental nutritional needs for an extended period of time. In the subject of hunger relief, the word "hunger" is used to refer to more than just the universal urge for food felt by all people. A famine is declared when there is an acute case of hunger, severe malnutrition, and individuals are beginning to die from starvation due to a lack of access to enough nourishing food. [FAO, 2012].

According to Wider Research, (2014) nutrition affects a child's thinking abilities, conduct, and health can be influenced by their nutrition and all of these have an impact on their academic achievement. According to studies, such as Gómez-Pinilla et al. (2008), diets rich in Trans and saturated fats can have a negative effect on memory and learning, early nutritional shortages can have an impact on how well school-aged children develop cognitively, and having access to food can help a child focus better and feel more energized. For instance, one study discovered that pupils in the fifth grade who consumed less nutrition fared poorly in a standardized literary evaluation (Florence, Asbridge, & Veugelers, 2008). According to another study, 5th graders who consumed greater processed meals performed worse on arithmetic and reading tests (Li & O'Connell, 2012).

Similar to this, a study that examined a healthy eating initiative that forbade the consumption of junk food in schools and initiated healthy and fresh prepared school meals discovered that students who participated in the initiative performed better on English and science exams compared to those who did not participate (Belot & James, 2009).

The way an individual eats affects how well s/he does in school thus, poor diet might make students more prone to illness or cause headaches and stomachaches, which can cause absences from class (Brown, Beardslee, & Prothrow-Stith, 2008). It has been demonstrated that giving children access to food that contains protein, carbs, and glucose enhances their memory, focus, and energy levels (Bellisle, 2004; Sorhaindo & Feinsein, 2006). On the other hand, when a child experiences nutritional deficiencies at early stage particularly those involving zinc, B vitamins, Omega-3 fatty acids, and protein, it can have an effect on how their brains develop (Sorhaindo & Feinsein, 2006). Additionally, studies indicate that diets high in Trans and saturated fats may have an adverse effect on the brain, affecting memory and learning (Gómez-Pinilla, 2008).

Chenoweth (2007) noted that a child's dietary health can have a direct impact on their mental capacity. For instance, even in its early stages, iron deficiency can reduce dopamine transmission, which has a detrimental effect on cognition. It has been demonstrated that deficiencies in other vitamins and minerals, particularly thiamine, vitamin E, vitamin B, iodine,

and zinc, impair cognitive function and mindfulness. Taking supplements like amino acids and carbohydrates can also enhance perception, intuition, and reasoning. According to Healthy Food Choices in School (2019), in the US, diets of pupils have been tested for more than 20 years by those who support children's health. They further noted that the results of early research that emphasized the advantages of student health improvement are clear thus, the behaviour and academic achievement of a child may be positively affected by increased good nutrition.

Sociologists and economics have focused increased attention on how diet and nutrition affect students' behavioral and academic performance. In general, studies demonstrate that a better diet is linked to improved academic achievement, and that initiatives aimed at promoting students' health also slightly raise their test scores in academic subjects. According to the study of Meyers, Sampson, Wietzman, Rogers, and Kayne, (1989), changing students' nutrition results in more frequent on-task behavior, higher arithmetic test scores, probably higher reading test scores, and higher attendance. Furthermore, replacing soft drinks in school vending machines with other drinks had a positive influence on behavioral outcomes such as tardiness and disciplinary reports (Price, 2012; Storey, Pearce, Ashfield-Watt, Wood, Baines, & Nelson, 2011)

Theoretical Framework

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory

Maslow's hierarchy provides a model for how students are motivated to learn. Without the bottom layer of the hierarchy met, students cannot reach the next level. Each level, once met, allows students the ability and motivation to learn. Each student can move up in the hierarchy with the proper support. The pyramid of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory is shown below:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Pupils and Teachers (Response Rate)

School	M	F	Teacher	No of Response	No of not Response	Total
1	10	10	2	22	4	26
2	10	14	2	26	2	28
3	8	12	2	22	3	25
4	12	14	2	28	2	30
5	6	8	2	16	1	17
Total	46	58	10	114	12	126

Response Rate

$$\text{Response: } \frac{114}{126} \times 100 = 90\%$$

Gender Rate

$$\text{M } \frac{51}{114} \times 100 = 44.7\%$$

Not Response:

$$\frac{12}{126} \times 100 = 10\%$$

$$\text{F } \frac{63}{114} \times 100 = 55.3\%$$

Table 2: Does hunger and malnutrition has combined threat on Child's ability to learn in School?

Schools	Strongly Agreed		Agreed		Neutral		Disagreed		Strongly Disagreed	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
1	10	45.5	8	36.4	1	4.5	2	9.1	1	4.5
2	8	30.8	10	38.5	3	11.5	4	15.4	1	3.8
3	10	45.5	7	31.8	1	4.5	3	13.7	1	4.5
4	10	35.7	12	43.0	2	7.1	2	7.1	2	7.1
5	5	31.3	7	43.8	1	6.2	2	12.5	1	6.2
Total	43		44		8		13		6	

Interpretation: Table 2 shows that 18(81.9%) of respondents agreed and strongly agreed with school 1, 1(4.5%) was neutral and 3(13.6%) disagreed and strongly disagreed. In school 2, 18(69.3%) strongly agreed and agreed while 3(11.5%) were neutral and 5(19.2%) disagreed and strongly disagreed. In school 3, 17(77.3%) agreed and strongly agreed, 1(4.5%) neutral and 4(18.2%) respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed. 22(78.7%) agreed and strongly agreed in school 4 while 2(7.1%) were neutral and 4(14.2%) were strongly disagreed and disagreed. In the last school, 12(75.1%) respondents were strongly agreed and agreed, 1(6.2%) neutral and 3(18.8%) disagreed and strongly disagreed. Hence, from the above analysis of school 1,2,3,4 and 5, it showed that hunger and malnutrition has combined threat on child's ability to learn in school.

Table 3: is there any relative contribution of hunger and malnutrition on the academic performance of Primary schools pupils in the Local Government Area?

Schools	Strongly Agreed		Agreed		Neutral		Disagreed		Strongly Disagreed	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
1	8	36.4	10	45.5	1	4.5	1	4.5	2	7.1
2	12	46.2	10	38.5	2	7.7	1	3.8	1	3.8
3	9	40.9	8	36.4	1	4.5	3	13.6	1	4.5
4	12	43.0	10	35.7	2	7.1	2	7.1	2	7.1
5	5	31.3	7	43.8	1	6.2	1	6.2	2	12.5
Total	46		45		7		8		8	

Interpretation: Table 3 shows that 18(81.9%) of respondents strongly agreed and agreed with school 1, 1(4.5%) was neutral and 3(13.6%) disagreed and strongly disagreed. In school 2, 22(84.7%) strongly agreed and agreed while 2(7.7%) of respondents were neutral and 2(7.6%) disagreed and strongly disagreed. In the third school, 17(77.3%) strongly agreed and agreed, 1(4.5%) was neutral while 4(18.1%) disagreed and strongly disagreed. In school 4, 22(78.7%) strongly agreed and agreed, 2(7.1%) respondents were neutral and 4(14.2%) disagreed and strongly disagreed. In the last school, 12(75.1%) strongly agreed and agreed while 1 (6.2%) was neutral and 3(18.7%) disagreed and strongly disagreed. Hence, from the above analysis of school 1, 2, 3, 4, &5, it was showed that there is relative contribution of hunger and malnutrition on the academic performance of primary schools pupils in the LGA.

The representative sample size was calculated with the aid of Yamane's 1967 formula of sample size as: $n = \frac{N}{1 + N*(e)^2}$

Where n= the sample size

N= the population

e= the acceptance sampling error

*= 90% confidence level error and

e= 0.10 are assumed

Data were collected from a total of 114 respondents out of the targeted 126. This translates to a response rate of 90% as calculated earlier.

Test of hypothesis using Pearson product movement correlation coefficient (ppmcc).

H01. Hunger and malnutrition has no significant combined threat on the child's ability to learn in school.

Table 4: observed frequency (Data from questions)

Response	Scale	Sch 1	2	3	4	5	Total
SA	5	10	8	10	10	5	43
A	4	8	10	7	12	7	44
U	3	1	3	1	2	1	8
D	2	2	4	3	2	2	13
SD	1	1	1	1	2	1	6
TOTAL	15	22	26	22	28	16	114

Tabular calculation for hypothesis 1

S/N	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
1.	5	43	25	1,849	215
2.	4	44	16	1,936	176
3.	3	8	9	64	24
4.	2	13	4	169	26
5.	1	6	1	36	6
	15	114	55	4,054	447

Analysis of Table: to apply the persons coefficient, the responses are grouped into (x) “independent variable” i.e. strongly agreed, agreed , undecided, disagreed ,strongly disagreed, using the scale of 5,4,3,2,1 respectively and (y) “Dependent variable” i.e. respondent’s response to each question. 0.10 is selected as a significant level having 90% confidence level. Reject Ho if it is less than critical value, otherwise accept Ho. This gives us the table below, which is used for testing hypothesis 1.

Person’s coefficient of correlation quantitative techniques formula is:

$$r = \frac{n\sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{5(447) - 15 (114)}{\sqrt{[5(55) - (15)^2] [5(4054) - (114)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{2235 - 1710}{\sqrt{[275 - 225] [20,270 - 12,996]}}$$

$$r = \frac{525}{\sqrt{50 \times 7274}}$$

$$r = \frac{525}{\dots}$$

$$r = \frac{\sqrt{363,700}}{603.07545}$$

$$r = 0.870537$$

$$r = 0.8705$$

Decision Rule:

Reject Ho if r is < tabulated value. Otherwise accept Ho

Accept H1 if r is > tabulated value. Otherwise reject Hi

0.10 is selected as the significant level having 90% confidence level.

Degree of freedom (d) = 0.10 for (n-2)

$$5-2= 3$$

0.10 at 3 degree freedom.

Using t- distribution for critical value for the level of significant at 0.10 and

3 degree of freedom= 2.35. From the foregoing r= 0.8705 which is less than the tabulated value= 2.35, the researcher therefore, regret the null hypothesis. Based on the sample evidence the test has statistically proven that there is significant combined threat of hunger & malnutrition on the child's ability to learn in school.

Ho₂: there is no significant relative contribution of hunger and malnutrition on the academic performance of primary schools pupils in Ikenne LGA.

Table 5: observe frequency (Data from questions)

Response	Scale	Sch 1	2	3	4	5	Total
SA	5	8	12	9	12	5	46
A	4	10	10	8	10	7	45
U	3	1	2	1	2	1	07
D	2	1	1	3	2	1	08
SD	1	2	1	1	2	2	08
TOTAL	15	22	26	22	28	16	114

Analysis of table: to apply the person's coefficient of correlation, the responses are grouped into (x) "independent variable" i.e. strongly agreed, agreed, undecided, disagreed, strongly disagreed, using the scale of 5,4,3,2,1 respectively and (y) "Dependent variable" i.e. respondent's response to each question. 0.10 is selected as a significant level having 90% confidence level. Reject Ho if it is less than critical value, otherwise accept Ho. This gives us the table below, which is used for testing hypothesis 2.

Person's coefficient of correlation quantitative techniques formula is:

$$r = \frac{n \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{[(n \sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2] [n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Tabular calculation for hypothesis 2

S/N	X	Y	Xy	X ²	Y ²
1.	5	46	230	25	2,116
2.	4	45	180	16	2,025
3.	3	7	21	9	49
4.	2	8	16	4	64
5.	1	8	8	1	64
	15	114	455	55	4,318

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2] [n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{\sqrt{(5 \times 455) - (15 \times 114)}}{\sqrt{[(5 \times 55) - (15)^2] [5(4318) - (114)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{2275 - 1710}{\sqrt{[275 - 225] [21,590 - 12,996]}}$$

$$r = \frac{565}{\sqrt{50 \times 8594}}$$

$$r = \frac{565}{\sqrt{429,700}}$$

$$r = \frac{565}{655.5150}$$

$$r = 0.861917$$

$$r = 0.8619$$

Decision Rule:

Reject Ho if r is < tabulated value. Otherwise accept Ho

Accept H1 if r is > tabulated value. Otherwise reject H1

0.10 is selected as the significant level having 90% confidence level.

Degree of freedom (d) = 0.10 for (n-2)

$$5-2=3$$

0.10 at 3 degree freedom.

Using t- distribution for critical value for the level of significant at 0.10 and

3 degree of freedom= 2.35. From the foregoing $r=0.8619$ which is less than the tabulated value= 2.35, the researcher therefore, regret the null hypothesis. Based on the sample evidence the test has statistically proven that the hunger and malnutrition has significant relative contribution on the academic performance of primary schools pupils in Ikenne L.G.A.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Throughout the whole life span of an individual, nutrition is a crucial pillar for survival, health, and development. Like "fuel" in a car, nutrition plays an important part in both human life and academic success. When the cells don't get the right nutritional fuel, they become sluggish and inadequate. The cells are like microscopic energy-producing machines, and much like machinery, they need to be properly maintained to stay in excellent operating order.

It is important to be aware of how hunger and malnutrition impair children's learning ability. Nutritional gardens should be introduced in school, and homes. The parents or guardians are in a position to influence the situation. The carers have a golden opportunity and window to influence the children's learning and eventual success in the world while they are still young. And changing their diet is one way to do that. Even though it may not always be simple, doing it is the best course of action.

Parents and guardians serve as the children's role models because they enjoy imitating their elders. They will be motivated to eat healthily if they observe their parents, guardians, and other family members doing so. Naturally, they will move out of that zone when we are their only influences and begin to be influenced by their friends in terms of eating. Therefore, there is need to provide them with a firm foundation and an understanding of the significance of good nutrition.

Declaration of Interest Statement

We certify that the manuscript we are submitting is original, has never been published, and not being considered for publication elsewhere.

References

- Bellisle, F. (2004). Effects of diet on behaviour and cognition in children. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 92(2), S227–S232. Retrieved from <http://hundsundskolerestaurant.no/wordpress/wpcontent/uploads/2010/11/Bellisle-sugar-and-cognition-in-children-2004.pdf>
- Belot, M., & James, J. (2009). Healthy school meals and educational outcomes. *Journal of Health Economics*, 30(3), 489-504.

- Brown, J. L., Beardslee, W. H., & Prothrow-Stith, D. (2008). Impact of school breakfast on children's health and learning: An analysis of the scientific research. Retrieved from the Sodexo Foundation website: http://www.sodexofoundation.org/hunger_us/Images/Impact%20of%20School%20Breakfast%20Study_tcm
- Bryan, J., Osendarp, S., Hughes, D., Calvaresi, E., Baghurst, K. & van Klinken, J. (2004). Nutrients for cognitive development in school-aged children. *Nutrition Reviews*, 62(8), 295–306.
- Centers for Disease Control. (2013). Childhood obesity facts. Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/healthyyouth/obesity/facts.htm>
- Chenoweth, W. (2007). Vitamin B complex deficiency and excess. In R. Kliegman, H. Jenson, R. Behrman, & B. Stanton (Eds.), *Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics*, 18th edition. Philadelphia: Saunders.
- Coleman-Jensen, A., Nord, M., & Singh, A. (2013). Household food security in the United States in 2012. Retrieved from United States Department of Agriculture Economic Research Service website: <http://www.ers.usda.gov/publications/err-economic-research-report/err155.aspx#.Um7t7BDHigl>
- Cueto, S. (2001). Breakfast and dietary balance: The enKid study. *Public Health Nutrition*, 4, 1429–1431.
- Delange, F. (2000) The role of iodine in brain development. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 59, 75–79.
- Sandstead, H. (2000). Causes of iron and zinc deficiencies and their effects on brain. *Journal of Nutrition*, 130, 347–349.
- Florence, M. D., Asbridge, M., & Veugelers, P. J. (2008). Diet quality and academic performance. *Journal of School Health*, 78(4), 209-215.
- Granholm, A. C., Bimonte-Nelson, H. A., Moore, A. B., Nelson, M. E., Freeman, L. R., & Sambamurti, K. (2008). Effects of a saturated fat and high cholesterol diet on memory and hippocampal morphology in the middle-aged rat. *Journal of Alzheimer's disease : JAD*, 14(2), 133–145. <https://doi.org/10.3233/jad-2008-14202>
- Greenbaum, L. (2007a). Vitamin E deficiency. In R. Kliegman, H. Jenson, R. Behrman, & B. Stanton (Eds.), *Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics*, 18th Edition. Philadelphia: Saunders.
- Greenbaum, L. (2007b). Micronutrient mineral deficiencies. In R. Kliegman, H. Jenson, R. Behrman, & B. Stanton (Eds.), *Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics*, 18th Edition. Philadelphia: Saunders.
- Gómez-Pinilla, F. (2008). Brain foods: The effects of nutrients on brain function. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 9(7), 568-578. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2805706/>
- Hanks, A., Just, D., Smith, L., & Wansink, B. (2012). Healthy convenience: Nudging students toward healthier choices in the lunchroom. *Journal of Public Health*, 34(3), 370-376.
- Hartline-Grafton, H., Henchy, G., & Levin, M. (2012). Healthier school meals: A summary of the new USDA standards for school breakfast and lunch. Retrieved from the Food Research and Action Center website: http://frac.org/pdf/school_meal_nutrition_rule_summary.pdf
- Hollar, D., Messiah, S., Lopez-Mitnik, G., Hollar, T., Almon, M., & Agatston, A. (2010). Effect of a two-year obesity prevention intervention on percentile changes in body mass index and academic performance in low income elementary school children. *American Journal of Public Health*, 100(4), 646–653.
- Li, J., & O'Connell, A. A. (2012). Obesity, high-calorie food intake, and academic achievement trends among U.S. school children. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 105(6), 391- 403.
- Long, M., Luedicke, J., Dorsey, M., Fiore, S., Henderson, S. (2013). Impact of Connecticut legislation incentivizing elimination of unhealthy competitive foods on National School Lunch Program participation. *American Journal of Public Health*, 103(7), 59-66.

- Minnesota Department of Health. (2012a). Children & adolescent overweight fact sheet. Retrieved from: <http://www.health.state.mn.us/cdr/obesity/pdfdocs/childrenoverweightfactsheet.pdf>
- Minnesota Department of Health. (2012b). Great Trays annual report, 2012. Retrieved from: http://www.health.state.mn.us/divs/hpcd/chp/cdr/nutrition/greattrays/pdfs/Great_Trays_Annual_Report_2012.pdf
- Minnesota Department of Health. (2013). The Minnesota Statewide Health Improvement Program SHIP progress brief – year 3. Retrieved from: <http://www.health.state.mn.us/divs/oshii/ship/docs/shiprpt2012.pdf>
- Murphy, J. M., Drake, J. E., & Weineke, K. M. (2005). Academics & Breakfast Connection Pilot: Final report on New York's classroom breakfast project. Retrieved from Nutrition Consortium of New York State website. http://www.gotbreakfast.org/news/NYS_bkfastinclass_studyresults_ABCfinal.pdf
- Powell, C., Walker, S., Chang, S., & Grantham-McGregor, S. (1998). Nutrition and education: A randomized trial of the effects of breakfast in rural primary school children. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 68, 873–879.
- Price, J. (2012). De-fizzing schools: The effect on student behavior of having vending machines in schools. *Agricultural and Resource Economics Review*, 41(1), 92–99.
- Redden, J., Wahlstrom, K., & Reicks, M. (2002). Children's perceived benefits and barriers in relation to eating breakfast in schools with or without universal school breakfast. *Journal of Nutrition Education & Behavior*, 34(1), 47-52.
- Sorhaindo, A., & Feinstein, L. (2006). What is the relationship between child nutrition and school outcomes? Retrieved from the Centre for Research on the Wider Benefits of Learning website: <http://www.learningbenefits.net/Publications/ResReps/ResRep18.pdf>
- Storey, H., Pearce, J., Ashfield-Watt, P., Wood, L., Baines, E., & Nelson, M. (2011). A randomized controlled trial of the effect of school food and dining room modifications on classroom behaviour in secondary school children. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 65, 32–38.